

ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational research was conducted to ascertain the status of implementation and the extent of problems encountered by implementers in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in the Fourth Congressional District of Iloilo for the school year 2014-2015. The participants of this study were the entire population of 21 ALS implementers from seven municipalities of the Fourth District of Iloilo. This research determined whether there was a significant relationship between the status of implementation in the Alternative Learning System and the extent of problems encountered by the ALS implementers. This study utilized the validated and reliability-tested survey questionnaire of Perocho (2012). The study employed means and standard deviations as descriptive statistics, the Kruskal Wallis Test, and Spearman's Rank rho as inferential statistics. It was found that the status of implementation as an entire group in terms of the Basic Literacy Program (BLP) was "very good." In contrast, in terms of the Accreditation and Equivalency Program, it was "excellent." The implementation of the Basic Literacy Program and Accreditation and Equivalency Program of seven municipalities and when categorized to municipality classification ranges from "excellent" to "very good." When taken as an entire group, the extent of problems encountered by Implementers in BLP and A and E Programs needed to be more serious. Moreover, the problems encountered by seven municipalities when categorized into municipality classification are "somewhat serious" to "not serious." The status of Implementation in ALS was the same regarding BLP and A and E Programs among the municipalities and municipality classification. The extent of problems encountered by ALS Implementers in BLP and A and E Programs was similar when categorized as Municipality and Municipality Classification. Finally, there was no significant relationship between the Status of Implementation and Problems Encountered in the Alternative Learning System in the Fourth Congressional District of Iloilo.

Keywords: *Status of Implementation, Alternative Learning System, Extent of Problems, Iloilo*

INTRODUCTION

Literacy is fundamental to the achievement of the quality of life of a person (Anjum, 2015). Literacy is more than an essential reading ability but an indication of how adults use written information to function in society. Youth and adults should acquire the literacy and lifelong skills necessary for a good job, decent earnings, and quality learning opportunities. Countries that are successful in endowing their population with literacy and lifelong skills are usually in a better position to meet the economic demands of operating in a globalized information economy (Bernal, 2019). A highly-literate population will better deal with governance issues in a highly diverse society (Apao et al., 2014).

As noted by UNESCO, illiteracy hampers a country's economic growth. The Dakar Framework aimed to reduce adult illiteracy by 50 percent. Nevertheless, it will be missed by a wide margin, with 800 million adults worldwide still unable to read or pen their names, especially in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa (Narayan, 2012). The said countries have been assailed with economic crises prompted by poverty attributed to illiteracy.

The Philippines is not exempted from the economic crisis brought about by poverty. Apao (2014) stated that the Philippines was found to have one of the highest poverty incidence rates in Southeast Asia, pegged at 15.5%, with poor people living with not enough resources to sustain their daily needs. The Out-of-School Children (OSC), Out-of-School Youth (OSYs), and Out-of-School Adults (OSAs) comprise the vast number of Filipino individuals who are most affected by poverty due to a lack of educational opportunities. As revealed in the Country Profile commissioned for the EFA Global Monitoring Report 2008, Education for All by 2015, sixteen million two hundred eighty-two thousand three hundred forty-three (16,282,343) out-of-school Filipino citizens comprised 20% of the 82M in 2004 (Apao et al., 2014).

Hence, the Philippine government, through the Department of Education, has implemented the Alternative Learning System (ALS) as a crucial component of Philippine education to provide every individual with access to quality primary education to reduce the illiteracy rate as envisioned in the Education for All (EFA) 2015 Philippine Plan of Action. Section 12.1 Rules XII of R.A 9155 stipulates that ALS is a parallel learning system to provide a viable alternative to the existing formal education instruction, encompassing both the non-formal and informal sources of knowledge and skills (Barrido, 2022).

ALS stands for ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM, a free education program implemented by the Department of Education (DepEd) under the Bureau of Alternative Education (BALS). ALS aims to open more educational opportunities for Filipino citizens of different interests, capabilities of demographic characteristics, socio-economic origins, and status, as well as address the needs of the marginalized group. The program cuts the time to finish high school, significantly cutting the expenses as well.

The Alternative Learning System (ALS) is a ladderized, modular, non-formal education program in the Philippines for dropouts in elementary and secondary schools, out-of-school youths, non-readers, working Filipinos, and even senior citizens. It is a part of the education system of the Philippines, but an alternative system only requires students to choose schedules according to their choice and availability.

The program has two different schematics for conducting instruction; school-based and community-based. Instructions in the school-based program are conducted on school campuses, while in the community-based program, formal instruction is conducted in community halls or private places. The ALS program follows uniform lesson modules for all academic subjects covering the sciences, mathematics, English, Filipino, social studies, and current events. Delivery of instructions is provided by government-paid instructors or by private non-government organizations.

Aside from schematics, the program has two levels; elementary and secondary. Students must start from the elementary level and then proceed to the high school level. Suppose a student is a graduate of elementary under a formal classroom system. In that case, the student is automatically admitted to the secondary levels depending on which year level the student stopped schooling.

An alternative Learning System is an alternative way of acquiring primary education for elementary and secondary comparable to formal education. In support of the goals of Education for All, it has made great strides in delivering its primary education and literacy development services for out-of-school youth, children, and adults (Barrido, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This descriptive-correlational type of research employed the one-shot survey design. Thus, the researcher assessed, evaluated, and described the status of ALS implementation and the extent of problems encountered by the implementers in the Fourth Congressional District of the Iloilo province. Descriptive research was used to describe the status of the Alternative Learning system's implementation, the extent of problems encountered by the implementers, and the significant differences of the extents when classified according to the Municipality in the Fourth Congressional District of the Province of Iloilo. Correlational research was used to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of the Alternative Learning System and the extent of problems encountered by the ALS implementers. This mixed methodology deeply describes the extent of ALS implementation in the fourth congressional district of Iloilo province.

Respondents. The respondents of this study were all ALS implementers in each Municipality in the Fourth Congressional District of the Iloilo province. This excluded the ALS implementers of Passi City because they do not belong to the Division of Iloilo. The respondents were purposively selected since the study aimed to determine the status of implementation and the extent of problems encountered by ALS implementers in the study locale. The study's respondents were the 21 ALS implementers in the Fourth Congressional District.

Data Collection Procedure. In gathering data, permission to conduct the study was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of Iloilo, and a copy was furnished to the District Supervisor per Municipality of the Fourth Congressional District of Iloilo. A schedule was set per Alternative Learning System Community Learning Center for the availability of the implementers to respond to the questionnaire. The respondents were briefed as to the purpose of the study prior to the administration of the research instrument, and the implementers were requested to answer. The gathered accomplished questionnaire was treated as confidential for data analyses. After filling out the questionnaire, they were gathered, tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistic tools.

Data Analysis Procedure. The gathered data was subjected to the following statistical procedures: *Frequency Count and Percentage*; these were used in describing the profile of the respondents per Municipality. *Mean*: The mean was applied to determine the extent of the ALS

implementation and the *responses' homogeneity and heterogeneity*. The deviation was used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the responses. *Kruskal Wallis Test* was used to ascertain if there are significant differences in the status of ALS implementation and the extent of problems encountered by the implementers in the Fourth Congressional District when categorized according to the municipality and municipality classification. *Spearman rho* was used to determine the relationship between the status of the implementation of the Alternative Learning System and the extent of problems encountered by the implementers in the Fourth Congressional District of Iloilo.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Status of the Implementation of ALS in Terms of Basic Literacy

The status of the implementation of ALS basic literacy in the alternative learning program of the 4th Congressional District, when taken as an entire group, was "very good" (M= 4.15, SD = 0.29). When they were classified as Municipalities, Dueñas (M= 4.04, SD = 0.00); Banate (M= 3.84, SD = 0.36); San Enrique (M= 3.90, SD = 0.24) was "very good" implementation of the ALS basic literacy program, while Anilao (M= 4.35, SD = 0.08); Barotac Nuevo (M= 4.33, SD = 0.11); Dingle (M= 4.33, SD = 0.16); and Dumangas (M= 4.25, SD = 0.46) have an excellent implementation of ALS Basic Literacy Program. When they were classified as the classification of Municipality first class

(M= 4.26, SD = 0.46), second class (M= 4.34, SD = 0.11) and the third class (M= 4.33, SD = 0.16) have "excellent" implementation of the ALS basic literacy program. In contrast, the fourth class (M=4.04, SD=0.31) has a "very good" implementation of the ALS Basic Literacy Program.

Status of Implementation of ALS in Terms of Accreditation and Equivalency

The status of the implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency of the 4th Congressional District, when taken as an entire group, was "excellent" (M= 4.25, SD = 0.32). When they were classified as Municipalities, Dueñas (M=4.00, SD = 0.00); Dingle (M= 4.02, SD = 0.13); San Enrique (M= 4.05, SD = 0.24) have "very good" implementation of ALS in terms of Accreditation and Equivalency Program, while Anilao (M= 4.37, SD = 0.10); Barotac Nuevo (M= 4.39, SD = 0.03); Banate (M= 4.27, SD = 0.40); and Dumangas (M= 4.46, SD = 0.42). have an "excellent" implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency. When they were classified as to classification of Municipality first class (M= 4.46, SD = 0.42), second class (M= 4.39, SD = 0.03), and fourth class (M= 4.22, SD = 0.28) have "excellent" implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency, while the third class (M=4.03, SD=0.13) have a "very good" implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency.

The Extent of Problems Encountered by ALS Implementers in Terms of Basic Literacy

The extent of problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of basic literacy of the 4th Congressional District, when taken as an entire group, was "less serious" (M= 2.37, SD = 0.62). When they were classified as Municipalities, Dueñas, Anilao, Barotac Nuevo, Dingle, Banate, and San Enrique were "less serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of basic literacy (M= 2.33, SD = 0.00; M= 2.03, SD = 0.10; M= 2.00, SD = 0.18; M= 2.22, SD = 0.13; M= 2.36, SD = 0.39; and M= 2.26, SD = 0.60) respectively; while Dumangas have "moderately serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of basic literacy, (M= 2.76, SD = 1.00). When classified as Municipality, the first class had "moderately serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers regarding basic literacy (M= 2.76, SD = 1.01), respectively. In contrast, the second class, third class, and fourth class had "less serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of basic literacy (M=2.00, SD=0.18; M= 2.22, SD = 0.13; and M= 2.26, SD = 0.27).

The Extent of Problems Encountered by ALS Implementers in Terms of Accreditation and Equivalency

The extent of problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of accreditation and equivalency of the 4th Congressional District when taken as an entire group was "less serious" (M= 2.41, SD = 0.68). When they were classified as Municipalities, Dueñas, Anilao, Barotac Nuevo, Dingle, Banate, and San Enrique were "less serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of accreditation and equivalency (M= 2.57, SD = 0.00; M= 2.08, SD = 0.07; M= 2.07, SD = 0.14; M=

2.57, SD = 0.10; M= 2.00, SD = 0.09; and M= 2.13, SD = 0.52) respectively; while Dumangas have "moderately serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of accreditation and equivalency, (M= 2.87, SD = 1.11). When they were classified as to the classification of Municipality, the first class have "moderately serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of accreditation and equivalency (M= 2.87, SD = 1.11), while the second class, third class, and fourth class had "less serious" problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of accreditation and equivalency, (M=2.07, SD=0.14; M= 2.57, SD = 0.10; and M= 2.19, SD = 0.27) respectively.

The Significant Difference in the Status of Implementation of ALS (Basic Literacy Program) when Categorized as to Municipality and Municipality Classification

Kruskal Wallis test results shown in Table 6 revealed no significant difference in the status of Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy when they were classified as to Municipality, $\chi^2(6) = 10.74$, $p = 0.097$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the status of Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy was not rejected when they were classified as Municipality. This means that the status of the Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy was the same when they were classified as Municipalities. There was no significant difference in the status of the Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy when classified as to Classification of Municipality, $\chi^2(3) = 0.34$, $p = 0.544$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy status was not rejected when classified as to Classification of Municipality. This means no group had a different status of Implementation of ALS in Basic Literacy than other groups.

The Significant Difference in the Status of Implementation of ALS (Accreditation and Equivalency Program) when Categorized as Municipality and Classification of Municipality

Kruskal Wallis test results shown in Table 7 revealed no significant difference in the status of implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when they were classified as Municipality, $\chi^2(6) = 7.88$, $p = 0.247$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the status of implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency was accepted when they were classified as Municipality. This means that the status of the implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when classified as a Municipality was the same. There was no significant difference in the status of implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when they were classified as to Classification of Municipality, $\chi^2(3) = 5.12$, $p = 0.163$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the status of implementation of ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency was not rejected when classified as to Classification of Municipality. This means that no group had a diverse status of implementation of ALS regarding accreditation and equivalency than other groups.

The Significant Difference in the Extent of Problems Encountered of ALS (Basic Literacy Program) when Categorized as to Municipality and Municipality Classification

Kruskal Wallis test results shown in Table 8 revealed no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in basic literacy when they were classified as to Municipality, $\chi^2(6) = 3.62$, $p = 0.728$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the status extent of problems encountered by ALS in basic literacy when they were classified as Municipality was accepted. This means that the extent of problems encountered by ALS in basic literacy when classified as Municipality was the same. There is no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in basic literacy when they were classified as to Classification of Municipality, $\chi^2(3) = 0.62$, $p = 0.543$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in basic literacy when they were classified as to Classification of Municipality was not rejected. This means that only groups had various extents of problems encountered ALS in basic literacy than other groups.

The Significant Difference in the Extent of Problems Encountered of ALS (Accreditation and Equivalency Program) when Categorized as to Municipality and Municipality Classification.

Kruskal Wallis test results shown in Table 9 revealed no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when they were classified as to Municipality, $\chi^2(6) = 6.69$, $p = 0.350$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when they were classified as Municipality was accepted. This means that the extent of problems encountered by ALS regarding accreditation and equivalency when classified as a

Municipality was the same. The extent of problems encountered by ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency was the same when they were classified as to Classification of Municipality, $\chi^2(3) = 0.68$, $p = 0.491$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency when they were classified as to Classification of Municipality was accepted. This means that only groups had various extents of problems encountered ALS in terms of accreditation and equivalency than other groups.

Relationships between the Status of Implementation and the Extent of Problems Encountered in Alternative Learning Systems

The Spearman rho result shown in Table 10 reveals no significant relationship between the Status of Implementation and Problems Encountered in the Alternative Learning System, $r = -0.203$, $p = 0.378$; Basic Literacy Status and Problems Encountered, $r = -0.301$, $p = 0.185$; Accreditation and Equivalency Status and Problems Encountered, $r = -0.287$, $p = 0.207$. The p-value was greater than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the Status of Implementation and Problems Encountered of Alternative Learning System Basic Literacy Status and Problems Encountered; Accreditation and Equivalency Status and Problems Encountered was accepted. This means that extent of problems encountered by ALS implementers is independent of the implementation of alternative learning systems in primary literacy status, accreditation, and equivalency status.

The status of the implementation of ALS A&E was "excellent" when taken as an entire group, while BLP was "very good." The BLP implementation of Anilao, Barotac Nuevo, Dingle, and Dumangas was "excellent," while, Dueñas, Banate, and San Enrique were "very good." The A and E Program implementation of Anilao, Barotac Nuevo, Banate, and Dumangas was "excellent"; on the other hand, Dueñas, Dingle, and San Enrique were "very good." When they were categorized according to municipality classification, the First, Second, and Third classes had "excellent" implementation in BLP. At the same time, the A and E were the First, Second, and Fourth. In BLP, the Fourth class was "very good," while in A&E, it was the Third class municipality.

When taken as an entire group, the extent of problems encountered by ALS implementers regarding BLP and the A & E Program was "not serious." The problems encountered by ALS implementers in terms of BLP and A&E when they were categorized as to Municipality and Municipality Classification, Dueñas, Anilao, Barotac Nuevo, Dingle, Banate, and San Enrique or Second, Third, and Fourth class were "not serious," while Dumangas or First class municipality encountered "somewhat serious" problems.

When categorized as Municipality and Municipality Classification, there was no significant difference in the status of the Implementation of ALS in BLP and A&E Programs.

There was no significant difference in the extent of problems encountered by ALS in BLP and A&E Programs when they were categorized as Municipality and Municipality Classification.

There was no significant relationship between the Status of Implementation and Problems Encountered by the Alternative Learning System.

CONCLUSION

BLP and A & E Program were adequately implemented in the 4th Congressional District of Iloilo. ALS Implementers, who were the front liners of the programs, had done their initiatives to implement them as often as possible.

The extent of Problems Encountered by ALS Implementers in terms of BLP and A&E Program in the 4th Congressional District of Iloilo was not severe. ALS implementers have encountered fewer problems in the implementation of ALS programs. The more they are exposed to the program, the more they become experienced ALS Implementers and the fewer problems they encounter. BLP and A & E Program were implemented correctly in different municipalities and when categorized to municipality classification.

The extent of problems encountered by ALS Implementers is the same when categorized into municipality and municipality classification. The status of the implementation of ALS Implementers did not affect the problems encountered. This means that the implementation status has no relation to the extent of problems they encountered.

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